

Pinagpala

PUBLISHING SERVICES

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ARTICLE PUBLICATION EVALUATION/ PEER-REVIEW RESULT

Title of Work: "ANTI-FIXERS CAMPAIGN: THE CASE OF LAND TRANSPORTATION OFFICE IN TARLAC CITY"			
Publication: World Education Connect Multi-Disciplinary e-Publication Volume IV, Issue V, May 2024			
Date Reviewed: May 14, 2024			
The information below consists of the summary of article publication evaluation/peer review results conducted by Pinagpala Publishing Services prior to the publication of the article:			
Areas for Evaluation/Review:	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Reviewer 3
Relevance of the contents to the topic	✓	✓	✓
Organization of the ideas presented	✓	✓	✓
Originality of the Material	✓	✓	✓
Other technical aspects (language used, accuracy and timeliness of the information)	✓	✓	✓
No. of Areas Achieved:	4	4	4
Decision:	ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION		
<i>*Legend: 4 Areas Achieved: Accepted for Publication, No Revisions Needed 3 Areas Achieved: Minor Revisions Needed Before the Publication 2 Areas Achieved: Major Revisions Needed Before the Publication 1-0 Areas Achieved: Not Accepted for Publication</i>			

Pinagpala Publishing Services Evaluators/Reviewers:

Reviewer 1

Reviewer 2

Reviewer 3

Note: PPS uses the double-blind peer review and evaluation where both reviewers and authors are unaware of each other's identities to mitigate the risk of prejudice on the side of the reviewers.

Certified Correct:

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